

SENSE OF BELONGING, ONLINE AGGRESSION, AND PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF FILIPINO GENERATION Z AND MILLENNIALS

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Sense of Belonging, Online Aggression, and Psychological Well-Being of Filipino Generation Z and Millennials

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Abstract

This study primarily aimed to investigate the impact of a sense of belonging and online aggression on the psychological well-being of Filipino Generation Z and Millennials. Moreover, it analyzed the levels of sense of belonging, online aggression, and psychological well-being; to determine whether there were significant differences among these variables. Through sampling, the respondents of the study were 200 Filipinos under Generation Z and Millennials residing in Calamba City, Laguna. Standardized and adopted questionnaires such as the Sense of Belonging Instrument (SOBI-A and SOBI-P), Cyber-Aggression Typology Questionnaire (CATQ), and Ryff's Psychological Well-being (PWB) were utilized as survey instruments. The results indicated that Filipino Generation Z and Millennials did not exhibit statistically significant differences (2.58, Low) on sense of belonging online aggression (1.38, Very Low), and psychological well-being (4.77, Somewhat Low). Moreover, sense of belonging did not impact online aggression (.592) However, online aggression impacted psychological well-being (18.6%). On the other hand, sense of belonging did not significantly impact psychological well-being (.432) Based on these findings, a program was proposed to provide awareness and to lessen online aggression among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials and to further improve and enhance their sense of belonging and psychological well-being.

Keywords: *sense of belonging, online aggression, psychological well-being, Generation Z, Millennials*

Introduction

Human psychology often examines the notion of belonging through the perspectives of social bonds and emotional ties. Belonging is a fundamental human drive that encompasses feelings of connection, acceptance, and recognition. The investigation starts by considering the influence of physical environments on cultivating a sense of belonging. Regardless of whether individuals reside in homes, workplaces, communities, or other places, the physical characteristics of these settings profoundly affect their sense of connection and attachment. Exploring how people perceive and interact with their environments can deepen our understanding of the dynamics of belonging. A sense of belonging involves more than merely forming connections with others.

According to Cherry (2023), it focused on obtaining acceptance, attention, and support from group members and reciprocating these feelings towards others. The desire to belong to a group can also result in alterations in behaviors, beliefs, and attitudes as individuals seek to align with the group's standards and norms.

Conversely, in an era dominated by digital connectivity and virtual networks, the idea of belonging expands beyond physical spaces to include the online realm. As individuals engage with the complexities of digital interactions, their need for connection, acceptance, and loyalty evolves in significant ways. The internet serves as a distinctive platform where people communicate with those who share similar interests, share experiences, and cultivate a sense of identity and belonging. From social media platforms and online forums to virtual gaming communities and digital support groups, the internet provides numerous opportunities for individuals to connect, form bonds, and gain recognition.

According to Zubernis (2023), individuals joined virtual communities for various reasons, such as enjoyment and the desire to belong. Research indicated that people often engaged in online communities to make friends or gain new knowledge, depending on the group's focus. Joining a virtual community could be an effective way to counteract social isolation and foster interaction with others. Surveys revealed that members highly valued the sense of belonging provided by online communities. Social support from these communities enhanced overall well-being and was linked to positive relationships and personal growth.

However, when it comes to fostering a sense of belonging, the online world presents unique challenges and complexities. As individuals form virtual connections through screens and algorithms, they encounter issues related to authenticity, identity formation, and social comparison. The absence of physical cues, combined with the curated nature of online personas, can obscure the line between genuine and superficial connections, complicating the pursuit of true belonging in the digital space. Additionally, the online environment is susceptible to problems such as exclusion, cyberbullying, and social stratification, all of which can affect individuals' sense of belonging and mental well-being.

According to recent national statistics cited in UNICEF (2019) in the Philippines, more than half of children aged 13 to 17 experienced cyber violence. The prevalence of cyberviolence among males stood at 44%, which was comparable to females' rate of 43%. Verbal abuse through the internet or phone accounted for one-third of the cyberviolence incidents reported by Filipino children, while sexual communications made up a quarter of these incidents. A UNICEF U-Report survey conducted in June 2019 across 30 countries indicated that over three-quarters of young adults considered social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat, and Twitter

as the primary locations for online harassment. The pervasive nature of online connections meant that issues like bullying persisted beyond school hours. According to the U-Report findings, 32% of respondents believed the government bore the primary responsibility for tackling online bullying, 31% held young people accountable, and 29% pointed to internet service providers. These results underscored the divided opinions on who should take the lead in combating online bullying, highlighting the importance of shared responsibility involving both young adults and children.

Studying how Filipinos perceive belonging, experience online aggression, and maintain psychological well-being is crucial, given the Philippines' unique cultural dynamics, the increasing influence of digital interactions on social behavior, and the mental health consequences associated with online activities. The relationship among these factors is intricate and multifaceted. Conversely, a strong sense of belonging can act as a protective factor against the harmful impacts of online aggression. Individuals who feel connected to their peers and community are better equipped to withstand online harassment and bullying. In contrast, encountering aggression online can erode one's sense of belonging and psychological health. Persistent exposure to online aggression may lead to feelings of isolation, anxiety, and sadness, adversely affecting overall well-being.

This research has contributed valuable insights into strategies for addressing online violence, fostering a sense of belonging, and enhancing psychological well-being in digital contexts. Promoting awareness involves advocating for ethical online conduct, fostering empathy, and promoting respectful communication. Establishing inclusive and supportive online environments can enhance individuals' sense of belonging and overall psychological health. Recognizing the interplay among these factors allows educators, policymakers, and mental health professionals to collaborate in creating safer and more supportive learning environments, whether in virtual spaces or physical settings.

Research Questions

The study determined the level of sense of belonging, online aggression, and psychological well-being of Filipino Generation Z and Millennials. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of sense of belonging among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials?
2. What is the level of online aggression among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials?
3. What is the level of psychological well-being among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials?
4. Does the level of sense of belonging among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials affect their level of online aggression?
5. Does the level of online aggression among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials affect their level of psychological well-being?
6. Does the level of sense of belonging among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials affect their level of psychological well-being?
7. Is there a significant difference between Filipino Generation Z and Millennials' levels of perceived sense of belonging, online aggression, and psychological well-being?
8. Based on the findings, what program may be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

This study primarily showed the impact of a sense of belonging and online aggression on the psychological well-being of Filipino Generation Z and Millennials. With this, it utilized a quantitative research method, specifically the causal-comparative research design. According to Sreekumar (2023), quantitative research methods involve examining occurrences that impact a specific group of individuals, known as the sample population.

Moreover, according to Lawrence (2023), causal-comparative research design was a non-experimental study that examined the effect of an independent variable on a dependent variable by comparing two or more groups of people. This further studied the impact of sense of belonging and online aggression to the psychological well-being of Filipino Generation Z and Millennials.

Respondents

In selecting the respondents in this study, stratified random sampling was utilized. As defined by Hayes (2023), stratified random sampling was a purposive sampling approach that divided a population into smaller subgroups known as strata. It enabled the selection of a sample population that most accurately represented the total population under study. In computing the sample population, this research used G*Power to help the researcher determine the smallest sample size that was suitable to detect the effect of a given test at the desired level of significance.

The purpose of this research was to measure the impact of a sense of belonging and online aggression on the psychological well-being of Filipino Generation Z and Millennials. Respondents of the study were under the range of each generation, with Generation Z (Gen Z) ages ranging to 11-26 years old, while Millennials range to 27-42 years old. They were chosen to be the respondents of the study since according to Alves (2023), Generation Z and Millennials were the first generation to integrate all manner of digital technology into their daily lives.

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

Sex\Generation	Generation Z (18-26)	Millennials (27-42)	Percentage
Male	50	50	50%
Female	50	50	50%
Total	200		100%

Instrument

The questionnaire consisted of demographic profiling and the three adopted scales. This study was anchored on the three adopted instruments, the Sense of Belonging Instrument (SOBI-P and SOBI-A) published by Hagerty and Patuský (1995, as cited in Leon-Martinez et al., 2021) Cyber Aggression Typology Questionnaire by Runions, Bak, and Shaw et. al. (2016, as cited in Runions et al., 2019), and Carol Ryff's (1989, as cited in Ryff, 2019) Psychological Well-being Scale. All of the instruments used for this study were open for public use and available for research purposes.

Sense of Belonging Instrument (SOBI-P and SOBI-A). This instrument was used to assess a sense of belonging. Bonnie Hagerty and Kathleen Patuský developed a 27-item self-report measure that included two distinct scales: the SOBI-P (psychological state), which measured sense of belonging in terms of valued involvement and fit in relationships, and the SOBI-A (antecedents), which investigated the antecedents to a sense of belonging. The assessment used a Likert-type scale with values ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree). A group of specialists assessed the content validity. Construct validity, internal consistency, and retest reliability were investigated in a series of studies involving three subjects. The results indicated that SOBI-P was a valid and reliable measure of sense of belonging. SOBI-A appeared to reflect an individual's motivation for a sense of belonging, but further investigation was needed on its construct validity and internal consistency.

Cyber Aggression Typology Questionnaire. This instrument was used to assess the severity of online aggression. Kevin Runions, Michael Bak, and Therese Shaw created a 29-item self-report questionnaire to discern four types of online aggression based on motivational valence and self-control. The approaches for exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis verified the original questionnaire's four-component model. The assessment used a 4-point Likert Scale with values ranging from 1 (extremely unlike me) to 4 (very like me). The questionnaire was structured around four factors: impulsive-aversive cyber-aggression, controlled-aversive cyber-aggression, controlled-appetitive cyber-aggression, and impulsive-appetitive cyber-aggression. The questionnaire demonstrated good discriminativeness and reliability; it could be used as a useful psychological diagnostic tool for examining cyber-aggression in both scientific and practical contexts. Understanding the motivations for cyber-aggressive behavior could aid in the development of novel preventive strategies that considered individual differences in the disadaptive aspects of online aggression.

Ryff's Psychological Well-being Scale. This instrument was used to assess psychological well-being. Carol Ryff created a 42-item self-report questionnaire to determine six components of well-being and happiness: autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relationships with others, purpose in life, and self-acceptance. The assessment used a 7-point Likert-type scale, with 1 indicating strong agreement and 7 indicating extreme disagreement. Initial paper found that the six scales had adequate internal consistency (α) ranging from .93 to .86. Furthermore, test-retest reliability over six weeks yielded values ranging from .88 to .81, indicating that questionnaire responses stayed rather constant over time in the absence of intervention. Overall, these results indicated that the questionnaire was reliable.

Procedure

Before collecting the data in measuring the impact of a sense of belonging and online aggression on the psychological well-being of Filipino Generation Z and Millennials, the researcher included a consent form for the respondents to allow themselves to willingly be part of the study. Data was collected through a Google form survey according to the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The adopted survey questionnaires which were the Sense of Belonging Instrument (SOBI-P and SOBI-A) published by Hagerty and Patuský (1995, as cited in Leon-Martinez et al., 2019), Cyber Aggression Typology Questionnaire by Runions et al. (2016, as cited in Runions et al., 2019) and Ryff's (1989, as cited in Ryff, 2019) Psychological Well-being Scale was plotted in Google form survey. Links were distributed online for the convenience of respondents and to maximize data retrieval. The data was organized using the extracted Google Excel from the survey form so that a professional statistician could analyze it. After the data had been analyzed, the conclusion and recommendations were made.

Data Analysis

To effectively interpret the data, the study used statistical treatment. The statistical techniques that were used in the treatment of the gathered data are as follows:

Mean was used to determine the levels of perceived sense of belonging, online aggression, and psychological well-being among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials.

t-test for Independent samples was used to compare the significant difference between psychological well-being and Filipino Generation Z and Millennials' levels of sense of belonging and online aggression.

Regression analysis was used to determine the significant impact of a sense of belonging and online aggression on the psychological well-being of Generation Z and Millennials.

Ethical Considerations

Given the sensitive nature of the subject, this study discussed the research objectives and provided full assurance that all responses were used for scholarly purposes only and were treated with strict confidentiality. This study employed the Data Privacy Act of 2012, otherwise known as Republic Act 10173 to ensure confidentiality of data accompanying an informed consent. The Philippine Government have strengthened the data privacy “to protect the fundamental human right of privacy, of communication while ensuring free flow of information to promote innovation and growth.” The respondents were humanely treated and were given the utmost respect. No other person was given access to obtain personal data gathered from the study.

A disclaimer was placed in the online test questionnaire regarding the Data Privacy. Respondents were encouraged to participate, but not at the expense of their privacy; they were allowed to remain anonymous and withhold certain information, including their name. Also, in order to obtain consent and approval prior to the use of instruments, a request to the author of the adopted tool was considered. The study also ensured that all information sources used were properly cited and acknowledged. Furthermore, the findings were shared with the institute in order for it to develop a comprehensive policy or program.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the interpretation and analysis of data gathered to discuss the answers to the research problems of the study. The study attempted to determine the level of sense of belonging, online aggression, and psychological well-being, and the impact of online aggression on psychological well-being, and the impact of sense of belonging on psychological well-being among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials.

Problem Number 1. What is the level of sense of belonging among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials?

The Sense of Belonging among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials was Low (Disagree 2.58) Furthermore, the indicator “I have qualities that can be important to others (R)” had the highest computed composite mean of 3.30 verbally interpreted as Strongly Disagree or Very Low. Meanwhile, the indicator “I could disappear for days, and it wouldn’t matter to my family (R)” had the lowest computed composite mean of 2.01 verbally interpreted as Agree or High.

It can be concluded that many individuals perceive their unique qualities as irrelevant when it comes to fitting in with a social group, which can worsen feelings of loneliness and inadequacy. Consequently, having a low sense of belonging may stem from believing that their attributes do not meet the group’s expectations and standards, leading them to adjust themselves to fit in.

Table 2. *Level of Sense of Belonging among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials*

<i>Indicators in terms of Sense of Belonging</i>		<i>Generation Z</i>		<i>Millennials</i>		<i>Composite</i>		Rank
		<i>X</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>X</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>X</i>	<i>VI</i>	
1.	I often wonder if there is any place on earth where I really fit in. (R)	2.78	D	2.54	D	2.66	D	11
2.	I am just not sure if I fit in with my friends. (R)	2.39	A	2.19	A	2.29	A	20
3.	I would describe myself as a misfit in most social situations. (R)	2.43	A	2.23	A	2.33	A	19
4.	I generally feel that people accept me (R)	2.65	D	2.84	D	2.75	D	10
5.	I feel like a piece of a jig-saw puzzle that doesn’t fit into the puzzle (R)	2.53	D	2.19	A	2.36	A	16
6.	I would like to make a difference to people or things around me, but I don’t feel that what I have to offer is valued (R)	2.77	D	2.42	A	2.60	D	12
7.	I feel like an outsider in most situations (R)	2.50	D	2.18	A	2.34	A	17.5
8.	I am troubled by feeling like I have no place in this world (R)	2.38	A	2.05	A	2.22	A	22.5
9.	I could disappear for days and it wouldn’t matter to my family (R)	2.15	A	1.86	A	2.01	A	27
10.	In general, I don’t feel a part of the mainstream of society (R)	2.25	A	1.97	A	2.11	A	26
11.	I feel like I observe life rather than participate in it (R)	2.59	D	2.39	A	2.49	A	13.5
12.	If I died tomorrow, very few people would come to my funeral (R)	2.29	A	2.15	A	2.22	A	22.5
13.	I feel like a square peg trying to fit into a round hole (R)	2.37	A	2.13	A	2.25	A	21
14.	I don’t feel that there is any place where I really fit in this world (R)	2.37	A	2.01	A	2.19	A	24
15.	I am uncomfortable that my background and experiences are so different from those who are usually around me (R)	2.52	D	2.24	A	2.38	A	15
16.	I could not see or call my friends for days and it wouldn’t matter to them (R)	2.56	D	2.41	A	2.49	A	13.5
17.	I feel left out of things (R)	2.47	A	2.20	A	2.34	A	17.5
18.	I am not valued by or important to my friends (R)	2.25	A	2.01	A	2.13	A	25
19.	It is important to me that I am valued or accepted by others	3.06	D	2.88	D	2.97	D	6
20.	In the past, I have felt valued and important to others	3.17	D	3.12	D	3.15	D	4
21.	It is important to me that I fit somewhere in this world	3.10	D	3.00	D	3.05	D	5
22.	I have qualities that can be important to others (R)	3.22	D	3.37	SD	3.30	SD	1
23.	I am working on fitting in better with those around me	2.94	D	2.82	D	2.88	D	9
24.	I want to be a part of things going on around me	2.95	D	2.90	D	2.93	D	7

25. It is important to me that my thoughts and opinions are valued	3.31	SD	3.16	D	3.24	D	2
26. Generally, other people recognize my strengths and good points	3.10	D	3.24	D	3.17	D	3
27. I can make myself fit in anywhere	2.87	D	2.97	D	2.92	D	8
General Assessment	2.67	D	2.50	D	2.58	D	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00, Strongly Disagree (SD) / Very Low; 2.50 – 3.24, Disagree (D) / Low; 1.75 – 2.49, Agree (A) / High; 1.00 – 1.74, Strongly Agree (SA) / Very High

Conversely, familial belonging holds significance because it offers essential support, connection, and a sense of belonging that influences individuals' development and well-being. Moreover, there seems to be a strong connection between a person's sense of self and their identity. When familial settings align with one's identity and beliefs, a strong sense of belonging within the family can be felt. However, if individuals feel that their identity does not match expectations or social standards elsewhere, they might feel less inclined to belong. Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs theory provides insight into this phenomenon. A lack of belonging can impact a person's self-esteem and hinder their ability to reach their full potential, as well as interfere with meeting higher-level needs, particularly the need for love and belonging.

This was supported by Cherry (2023) explained that when people attempted to conform to the group's expectations and standards, the desire to belong influenced their attitudes, beliefs, and actions. Individuals also spent a large amount of time assessing their level of fit in the group by comparing themselves to other members. As a result of this social comparison, individuals might have adopted some of the more well-known group members' attitudes and behaviors in attempt to fit in and be accepted.

In addition, Rejaän et al. (2021) highlighted the significant role of children's internal working models of connections to others, emphasizing that the need to belong remained a powerful motivator for interpersonal interactions. A strong sense of belonging was crucial for effective adjustment, especially during adolescence, when social interactions outside the home gained importance and young people sought a balance between autonomy and relatedness in their relationships.

Moreover, according to Mcleod (2024) Maslow believed a person must have fulfilled their basic survival needs before addressing higher-level needs. Environmental and interpersonal challenges often complicated meeting these higher-level needs. Individuals had to first satisfy lower-level deficit needs before progressing to higher-level growth needs. While everyone had the potential to move up the hierarchy and strive for self-actualization, the lack of basic needs could often hinder this progress. In addition to Maslow's hierarchy of needs, removing barriers to belonging, such as prejudice or social isolation, is crucial for promoting overall well-being and personal development.

Problem Number 2. What is the level of online aggression among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials?

The Online Aggression of Filipino Generation Z and Millennials was Very Low (Very Unlike Me, 1.38) Furthermore, the indicator "If I see a message online that gets me angry, I react too quickly and then regret the way I respond" had the highest computed composite mean of 1.62 verbally interpreted as Strongly Disagree or Very Low. Meanwhile, the indicator "I like using my electronic device(s) to plan my revenge when I feel angry at someone" had the lowest computed composite mean of 1.24 verbally interpreted as Strongly Disagree or Very Low.

The findings imply that, while Filipino culture exhibits low levels of online aggression, how conflicts are expressed and resolved in online interactions is influenced by cultural norms emphasizing respect, harmony, collective identity, face-saving, and conflict-resolution methods.

In contrast to cultures that prioritize individualism, these cultural elements lead to a more subtle and indirect manifestation of online aggression. Rather than escalating aggression, individuals lean towards seeking reconciliation and restoring harmony. Moreover, the practice of self-control is crucial for managing emotions, understanding others, resolving conflicts constructively, delaying gratification, staying aligned with personal values, and taking responsibility for one's actions. This accounts for the lower incidence of online aggression among Filipinos. Encouraging self-control within the Filipino community fosters more courteous, empathetic, and peaceful online interactions.

This was based on Madrona et al. (2023) The Philippines, known for its diversity, exhibited a rich tapestry of cultures, much like the varied villages scattered across the archipelago. Undoubtedly, "Filipino culture" could be seen as a blend of indigenous and colonial influences, encompassing values, beliefs, practices, and traditions. Family stood at the core of Filipino culture, with the actions of any family member impacting others profoundly. It was observed that piety and respect served as crucial guiding principles in the lives of Filipino adolescents.

Additionally, the concept of kindness, known as "kagandahang loob," was highlighted as a core value, representing a mutual nobility manifested through spontaneous acts of kindness stemming from the goodness of the heart.

On the other hand, according to Caorong (2022), some individuals possessed strong self-control achieved through a deliberate regulatory process encompassing various subcomponents. This process involved the capacity to adjust and oversee one's actions while foreseeing consequences, delaying gratification, restraining harmful behavior, and maintaining a focus on objectives. In contrast, weak self-control tended to be more impulsive, hampering the capacity for planning, delaying immediate gratification, and effectively adapting behavior.

Table 3. Level of Online Aggression among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials

Indicators in terms of Online Aggression	Generation Z		Millennials		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. If someone tries to hurt me, I will use an electronic device to immediately get back at them	1.38	VUM	1.48	VUM	1.43	VUM
2. If someone does something to hurt me, I would get back at them in my own time by using my electronic device(s)	1.46	VUM	1.43	VUM	1.45	VUM
3. If I don't like someone, I use the internet to turn others against them	1.31	VUM	1.30	VUM	1.31	VUM
4. I get carried away having fun online and others think I'm being a cyberbully or a troll	1.43	VUM	1.40	VUM	1.42	VUM
5. If I get teased or threatened, I get angry easily and strike back online right away	1.31	VUM	1.33	VUM	1.32	VUM
6. If someone tries to hurt me, I will use my electronic device(s) to get back at them in my own time	1.32	VUM	1.29	VUM	1.31	VUM
7. Sometimes I'll team up with my friends to bring someone down online	1.41	VUM	1.32	VUM	1.37	VUM
8. I use an electronic device to get back at someone as soon as they post a harmful message about me	1.47	VUM	1.44	VUM	1.46	VUM
9. I make fun of people I don't know on the internet without thinking about whether they will see it or not	1.47	VUM	1.36	VUM	1.42	VUM
10. If someone makes me angry online I quickly post mean texts and messages online	1.30	VUM	1.24	VUM	1.27	VUM
11. I get back at people who make fun of me on the internet because their posts hurt more the more I think about them	1.45	VUM	1.36	VUM	1.41	VUM
12. If someone makes fun of me on the internet, I get frustrated and respond angrily online right away	1.36	VUM	1.38	VUM	1.37	VUM
13. Sometimes I can be mean to people online to get what I want	1.42	VUM	1.34	VUM	1.38	VUM
14. If I'm having fun and joking online, I don't care if someone's feelings get hurt	1.41	VUM	1.42	VUM	1.42	VUM
15. I overreact before I have a chance to think about the consequences when someone says something mean online	1.56	VUM	1.46	VUM	1.51	VUM
16. If I see a message online that gets me angry, I react too quickly and then regret the way I respond	1.66	VUM	1.58	VUM	1.62	VUM
17. When I don't like a person, I use the Internet to make them feel like they do not belong in my group	1.26	VUM	1.27	VUM	1.27	VUM
18. If someone tries to cyberbully me, I quickly lash back with something online	1.49	VUM	1.38	VUM	1.44	VUM
19. I repeatedly annoy people online because I think it's funny	1.27	VUM	1.33	VUM	1.30	VUM
20. If someone says something online to hurt me, I post something back right away to get back at them	1.32	VUM	1.28	VUM	1.30	VUM
21. I like using my electronic device(s) to plan my revenge when I feel angry at someone	1.19	VUM	1.28	VUM	1.24	VUM
22. If somebody criticizes me online or in a text, I often react aggressively without thinking of the consequences	1.29	VUM	1.31	VUM	1.30	VUM
23. If I need to get revenge on someone, I would rather strike back using my electronic device(s) where I can plan out how to do it	1.27	VUM	1.26	VUM	1.27	VUM
24. I pretend to be someone else online to ruin somebody else's friendships	1.29	VUM	1.22	VUM	1.26	VUM
25. I hastily respond to something written online and regret it later	1.39	VUM	1.34	VUM	1.37	VUM
26. If I see a mean message about me on my electronic device, it bothers me more and more when I think about it, and I try to get even	1.68	VUM	1.46	VUM	1.57	VUM
27. I respond very quickly to a message or post that is disrespectful to me	1.81	SUM	1.64	VUM	1.73	VUM
28. I have at times used the internet to make someone look bad	1.35	VUM	1.26	VUM	1.31	VUM
29. Joking online is so much fun that I don't worry about whether someone might be bothered by what I say.	1.36	VUM	1.35	VUM	1.36	VUM
General Assessment	1.40	VUM	1.36	VUM	1.38	VUM

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00, Very Like Me (VLM) / Very High; 2.50 – 3.24, Somewhat Like Me (SLM) / High; 1.75 – 2.49, Somewhat Unlike Me (SUM) / Low; 1.00 – 1.74, Very Unlike Me (VUM) / Very Low

Problem Number 3. What is the level of psychological well-being among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials?

Table 4.1. Level of Psychological Well-being among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials

Indicators in terms of Psychological Well-being	Generation Z		Millennials		Composite		Rank
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI	
1. "I am not afraid to voice my opinions, even when they are in opposition to the opinions of most people." (R)	5.58	SoD	5.53	SoD	5.56	SoD	15
2. "For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing, and growth." (R)	6.82	SD	6.69	SD	6.76	SD	1
3. "In general, I feel I am in charge of the situation in which I live." (R)	6.32	SD	6.27	SD	6.30	SD	3
4. "People would describe me as a giving person, willing to share my time with others." (R)	6.30	SD	6.22	SD	6.26	SD	4

5.	“I am not interested in activities that will expand my horizons.”	5.89	SoD	5.62	SoD	5.76	SoD	11.5
6.	“I enjoy making plans for the future and working to make them a reality.” (R)	4.83	ALD	5.47	SoD	5.15	ALD	19
7.	“Most people see me as loving and affectionate.” (R)	6.02	SoD	6.00	SoD	6.01	SoD	7
8.	“In many ways I feel disappointed about my achievements in life.”	2.88	ALA	3.51	ALA	3.20	ALA	39
9.	“I live life one day at a time and don't really think about the future.”	3.78	NAD	3.89	NAD	3.84	NAD	32
10.	“I tend to worry about what other people think of me.”	2.76	ALA	3.47	ALA	3.12	ALA	40
11.	“When I look at the story of my life, I am pleased with how things have turned out.” (R)	5.76	SoD	5.81	SoD	5.79	SoD	10
12.	“I have difficulty arranging my life in a way that is satisfying to me.”	2.63	SoA	3.45	ALA	3.04	ALA	41
13.	“My decisions are not usually influenced by what everyone else is doing.” (R)	5.63	SoD	5.56	SoD	5.60	SoD	14
14.	“I gave up trying to make big improvements or changes in my life a long time ago.”	4.33	NAD	4.36	NAD	4.35	NAD	25
15.	“The demands of everyday life often get me down.”	3.18	ALA	3.87	NAD	3.53	ALA	35
16.	“I have not experienced many warm and trusting relationships with others.”	4.59	ALD	4.50	ALD	4.55	ALD	22
17.	“I think it is important to have new experiences that challenge how you think about yourself and the world.” (R)	6.47	SD	6.28	SD	6.38	SD	2
18.	“Maintaining close relationships has been difficult and frustrating for me.”	4.17	NAD	4.38	NAD	4.28	NAD	28
19.	“My attitude about myself is probably not as positive as most people feel about themselves.”	3.10	ALA	3.70	NAD	3.40	ALA	36
20.	“I have a sense of direction and purpose in life.” (R)	5.77	SoD	5.87	SoD	5.82	SoD	9

Table 4.2. Level of Psychological Well-being among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials

	Indicators in terms of Psychological Well-being	Generation Z		Millennials		Composite		Rank
		X	VI	X	VI	X	VI	
1.	“I judge myself by what I think is important, not by the values of what others think is important.” (R)	5.52	SoD	5.41	SoD	5.47	SoD	17
2.	“In general, I feel confident and positive about myself.” (R)	4.34	NAD	4.67	ALD	4.51	ALD	23
3.	“I have been able to build a living environment and a lifestyle for myself that is much to my liking.” (R)	5.70	SoD	5.56	SoD	5.63	SoD	13
4.	“I tend to be influenced by people with strong opinions.”	2.93	ALA	3.48	ALA	3.21	ALA	38
5.	“I do not enjoy being in new situations that require me to change my old familiar ways of doing things.”	3.59	NAD	3.88	NAD	3.74	NAD	33
6.	“I do not fit very well with the people and the community around me.”	4.41	NAD	4.89	ALD	4.65	ALD	20.5
7.	“I know that I can trust my friends, and they know they can trust me.” (R)	6.19	SD	6.02	SoD	6.11	SoD	6
8.	“When I think about it, I haven't really improved much as a person over the years.”	4.06	NAD	4.51	ALD	4.29	NAD	27
9.	“Some people wander aimlessly through life, but I am not one of them.” (R)	4.69	ALD	4.60	ALD	4.65	ALD	20.5
10.	“I often feel lonely because I have few close friends with whom to share my concerns.”	4.23	NAD	4.21	NAD	4.22	NAD	29
11.	“When I compare myself to friends and acquaintances, it makes me feel good about who I am.” (R)	4.25	NAD	4.02	NAD	4.14	NAD	30
12.	“I don't have a good sense of what it is I'm trying to accomplish in life.”	4.02	NAD	4.64	ALD	4.33	NAD	26
13.	“I sometimes feel as if I've done all there is to do in life.”	4.15	NAD	4.06	NAD	4.11	NAD	31
14.	“I feel like many of the people I know have gotten more out of life than I have.”	3.04	ALA	3.64	NAD	3.34	ALA	37
15.	“I have confidence in my opinions, even if they are contrary to the general consensus.” (R)	5.27	ALD	5.36	SoD	5.32	SoD	18
16.	“I am quite good at managing the many responsibilities of my daily life.” (R)	5.60	SoD	5.36	SoD	5.48	SoD	16
17.	“I have the sense that I have developed a lot as a person over time.” (R)	5.99	SoD	5.72	SoD	5.86	SoD	8
18.	“I enjoy personal and mutual conversations with family members and friends.” (R)	6.25	SD	6.07	SoD	6.16	SD	5
19.	“My daily activities often seem trivial and unimportant to me.”	4.26	NAD	4.47	ALD	4.37	NAD	24
20.	“I like most parts of my personality.”	5.81	SoD	5.71	SoD	5.76	SoD	11.5
21.	“It's difficult for me to voice my own opinions on controversial matters.”	3.25	ALA	3.88	NAD	3.57	ALA	34
22.	“I often feel overwhelmed by my responsibilities.”	2.31	SoA	3.12	ALA	2.72	ALA	42
General Assessment		4.68	ALD	4.85	ALD	4.77	ALD	

Legend: 6.16 – 7.00, Strongly Disagree (SD) / Very Low; 5.30 – 6.15, Somewhat Disagree (SoD) / Low; 4.44 – 5.29, A Little Disagree (ALD) / Somewhat Low; 3.58 – 4.43, Neither Agree nor Disagree (NAD) / Moderate; 2.72 – 3.57, A Little Agree (ALA) / Somewhat High; 1.86 – 2.71, Somewhat Agree (SoA) / High; 1.00 – 1.85, Strongly Agree (SA) / Very High

The Psychological Well-being of Filipino Generation Z and Millennials was Somewhat Low (A Little Disagree, 4.77) However, the indicator “For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing, and growth.” had the highest computed composite mean of 6.76 verbally interpreted as Strongly Disagree or Very Low. Meanwhile, the indicator “I often feel overwhelmed by my responsibilities” had the lowest computed composite mean of 2.72 verbally interpreted as A Little Agree or Somewhat High.

It can be concluded that this could be due to various factors such as societal, economic, and cultural influences; both generations place importance on personal fulfillment and self-improvement. People view learning as a means to expand their horizons, recognizing that acquiring new skills and knowledge is vital for staying competitive and achieving long-term career goals. However, for some individuals, concerns about financial stability can lead to feelings of overwhelm as they struggle to meet their basic needs and responsibilities. Consequently, additional significant factors might contribute to individuals' difficulty in effectively managing their obligations.

According to the Psychological Well-being theory, both environmental mastery and personal growth domains played crucial roles in promoting psychological health and enabling individuals to lead happy, fulfilling lives.

According to Eures (2021), individuals belonging to Generation Z and Millennials exhibited a strong inclination towards lifelong learning, constantly sought avenues for personal and professional growth. They prioritized employers who offered mentorship, development programs, and training opportunities. These generations were characterized by passion and loyalty, and companies that fostered their development and delineated clear paths for career advancement stood to gain significant benefits. Creating environments that facilitated continual learning and acknowledging their achievements fostered a positive workplace culture, stimulated creativity, and potentially augmented their psychological well-being.

On the other hand, Medaris (2023) referred to a survey commissioned by the American Psychological Association, which revealed that individuals aged 18 to 34 reported an average stress level of 6.4 out of 10, while those aged 65 and above reported an average stress level of 3.4. Despite this, younger demographics reported experiencing the most pronounced stress-related symptoms. Around two-thirds of respondents aged 18 to 34 expressed that stress adversely affected their ability to concentrate (67%) and felt that their anxiety went unnoticed by others (66%). Additionally, individuals in this age group were more likely to describe their stress as "completely overwhelming" (58%), leading to feelings of numbness (50%), and frequent impairment in daily functioning due to stress.

Problem Number 4. Does the level of sense of belonging among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials affect their level of online aggression?

Table 5. *Regression Analysis on the Impact of Sense of Belonging on Online Aggression among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials*

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Decisions	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	1.272	.209		6.085	.000		Not Significant
Sense of Belonging	.043	.080	.038	.537	.592	Accept Ho	

Dependent Variable: Online Aggression

R - Square = .038 F-value = .289
Adjusted R Square = .001 Significance = .592

Sense of Belonging did not significantly impact Online Aggression among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials. The probability value of .592 was greater than the level of significance at .05, thus accepting the null hypothesis.

While a sense of belonging impacts behavior in diverse ways, its influence on levels of online aggression may not always be significant owing to the intricate interplay of factors within online environments. Various factors come into play in influencing online aggression. For instance, anonymity allows certain individuals to feel less bound by social norms and more inclined to engage in aggressive behavior, irrespective of their sense of belonging to a specific online community. Additionally, norms and reinforcement contribute to an individual's behavior as social influences shape their actions. Moreover, psychological factors such as individual differences in personality traits, emotional regulation skills, and cognitive biases also affect how a sense of belonging influences online behavior.

According to Guo et. al. (2023), they discovered that anxiety preceded aggression and was significantly and positively linked with both conventional and online violence. They argued that anxiety might have heightened people's susceptibility to negative emotions and exacerbated adverse experiences, leading to increased aggression. In essence, individuals experiencing high levels of stress might also have exhibited heightened online aggressiveness. Those with elevated anxiety levels tended to be more responsive to negative stimuli and prone to impulsive actions.

On the other hand, Piccoli et. al. (2020) noted that within the realm of contextual factors, social influence mechanisms, including peer group dynamics, played a pivotal role in nurturing cyberbullying behaviors. Individuals often adjusted their behaviors, beliefs, and attitudes to align with group norms, a phenomenon termed social influence. Likewise, heightened perceived support for online hostility within peer groups correlated with an increased likelihood of individuals perpetrating such acts.

According to Jiang et. al. (2020), prior research uncovered associations between difficulties in emotion regulation and various mental health issues, interpersonal difficulties, and challenges in adaptation. According to the process model of emotion regulation, effective emotional regulation offered the capacity to inhibit or diminish ongoing expressions of unpleasant emotions. Maladaptive coping strategies often resulted in aggressive and hostile behavior as a means of dealing with negative emotions. Likewise, inadequate emotion management was predictive of future instances of relational aggression.

Problem Number 5. Does the level of online aggression among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials affect their level of psychological well-being?

Table 6. Regression Analysis on the Impact of Online Aggression on Psychological Well-being among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Decisions	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	5.139	.148		34.761	.000		
Online Aggression	-.269	.101	-.186	-2.658	.009	Reject Ho	Significant

Dependent Variable: Psychological Well-being
R - Square = .186 F-value = 7.063
Adjusted R Square = .034 Significance = .009

Based on the findings, Online Aggression significantly impacted the Psychological Well-being of Filipino Generation Z and Millennials. The probability value of .009 was lesser than the level of significance at .05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis. The results of the study revealed that Online Aggression significantly impact Psychological Well-being among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials by 18.6%.

This means that online aggression has an impact on the perpetrator's psychological well-being. These factors can lead to adverse psychological outcomes, encompassing emotional and social strain. Several interconnected factors associated with online aggression influence psychological well-being. These factors encompass social exclusion, which leads to social repercussions such as being blocked, unfollowed, or ostracized by others; and ethical quandaries, wherein individuals may experience guilt or shame for their actions, particularly if they perceive them as harmful and unjustifiable. Such experiences may detrimentally affect social well-being and self-esteem, consequently impacting psychological well-being negatively. Additionally, the normalization of aggression desensitizes individuals to the harm they inflict over time, diminishing empathy and compassion. This ethical decline engenders moral dissatisfaction and internal conflict, further exacerbating the negative impact on psychological well-being. However, individual traits such as personality, coping mechanisms, and social support networks exert distinct influences on the psychological well-being of individuals engaging in online aggression.

Based on Vosse (2023), studies indicated that the repercussions of actions impacted both victims and perpetrators, often resulting in feelings of guilt and humiliation. While guilt typically accompanied remorse, anxiety, and regret, shame was often associated with emotions of worthlessness or exposure. Surprisingly, these distinct emotions elicited different behavioral responses. Guilt tended to prompt reparative actions, whereas individuals experiencing shame might have adopted defensive behaviors, seeking to escape or conceal their actions. Termed 'moral' emotions, guilt and shame purportedly played a role in promoting kindness and discouraging antisocial behavior. Regarding the prevalence of these emotions, research suggested that offenders seldom experienced shame and guilt following a transgression. Moreover, older generations were more inclined to experience shame and guilt compared to younger generations, which could be linked to the historical rarity of these emotions in modern society.

On the other hand, based on Cuncic (2023), individuals engaging in online aggression might have grappled with underlying mental health issues that contributed to or exacerbated their aggressive conduct. Some individuals might have contended with behavioral challenges such as heightened aggressiveness, hyperactivity, or impulsivity, alongside issues related to substance misuse. Moreover, individuals exhibiting personality traits aligned with the "dark tetrad" of psychopathy—including Machiavellianism (characterized by deception and manipulation), sadism (deriving pleasure from inflicting harm), and narcissism—might have been predisposed to online harassment.

Problem Number 6. Does the level of sense of belonging among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials affect their level of psychological well-being?

Based on the findings, Sense of Belonging did not significantly impact Psychological Well-being among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials. The probability value of .432 was greater than the level of significance at .05, thus accepting the null hypothesis.

The results implied that belonging to a community or group does not automatically translate to having meaningful or supportive relationships that affect psychological well-being positively. Despite being part of a social group, individuals might experience feelings of loneliness or alienation if their connections are superficial, lack support, or lack depth. It is important to recognize that mental health is multifaceted, and well-being is influenced by a blend of biological, psychological, socioeconomic, and cultural elements.

Brower (2022) believed that there was more to belonging than merely fitting in with the group. A social identity, or a set of common values or beliefs, was closely related to belonging. An individual needed to sense unity and a shared sense of character with other group

members in order to feel fully included in the group. It went without saying that belonging was the experience of being a part of a community or group. It was the conviction that one was a member of a group or entity. People might have felt attached, connected, and fully accepted because of it. But as was mentioned earlier, being a part of a group was not the only thing that constituted belonging. Belonging was closely associated with a social identity, which was a collection of shared values or beliefs. A genuine sense of belonging required harmony and a set of values that the group's members shared.

Table 7. Regression Analysis on the Impact of Sense of Belonging on Psychological Well-being among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Decisions	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	5.002	.303		16.513	.000		
Sense of Belonging	-.091	.116	-.056	-.787	.432	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Dependent Variable: Psychological Well-being
 R-Square = .056 F-value = .620
 Adjusted R Square = .003 Significance = .432

On the other hand, according to Dhanabhakym and Sarath (2023), it was evident that psychological well-being was a complex construct that was influenced by a variety of individual and social factors, and that interventions such as mindfulness-based practices, cognitive-behavioral therapy, and physical activity could enhance well-being. Psychological well-being included life satisfaction, positive emotions, low levels of negative emotions, autonomy, good relationships, a feeling of purpose, and personal development. These components were linked and could impact one another, resulting in improved overall well-being. Maintaining a high level of psychological well-being was essential for living a fulfilling life while enhancing overall health and happiness.

Problem Number 7. Is there a significant difference between Filipino Generation Z and Millennials' levels of perceived sense of belonging, online aggression, and psychological well-being?

There was no significant difference in the assessment of the Filipino Generation Z and Millennials on levels of online aggression and psychological well-being. The generated computed probability values of online aggression, and psychological well-being were .546 and .079, respectively which were greater than the level of significance of 0.05; thus, accepting the null hypothesis

Table 8. The Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of the Filipino Generation Z and Millennials on Levels of Sense of Belonging, Online Aggression, and Psychological Well-being

Sub-variables			Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F Ratio	Sig.	Remarks	Decision
Sense of Belonging	Groups	Between	1.389	1	1.389	8.317	.004	Significant	Reject Ho
		Within	33.077	198	.167				
		Total	34.466	199					
Online aggression	Groups	Between	.080	1	.080	.366	.546	Not Significant	Accept Ho
		Within	43.543	198	.220				
		Total	43.624	199					
Psychological Well-being	Groups	Between	1.421	1	1.421	3.113	.079	Not Significant	Accept Ho
		Within	90.387	198	.457				
		Total	91.808	199					

Level of significance 0.05

The results indicated that both generations are similar regarding the measured factors, suggesting that Generation Z and Millennials do not exhibit significant distinctions from one another. Despite possible variations in their experiences, attitudes, and behaviors, Millennials and Generation Z seem to share commonalities and face similar challenges concerning psychological well-being, online aggression, and a sense of belonging across generations. Despite each generation's distinct characteristics, their common cultural influences and close age proximity often result in similarities being apparent.

In terms of their sense of belonging, according to Bakhtiari (2024), this phenomenon presented a peculiar paradox: despite Generation Z's extensive connectivity in the digital realm, they experienced social isolation. However, Camara (2023) noted that while Millennials were more inclined to socialize online than previous generations, their ultimate aim was to cultivate enduring relationships that extended beyond the digital realm. Many within this group prioritized face-to-face interaction and communal activities, viewing them as opportunities to forge genuine interpersonal connections and foster community bonds. Nevertheless, not all Millennials experienced a profound sense of belonging. Some respondents expressed uncertainty regarding the exact definition of belonging or its significance in their lives.

As mentioned by Gillis (2020), Generation Z and Millennials were known as digital natives. These generations had grown up surrounded by computers, digital devices, and social media. This immersion had given them a high degree of digital literacy, enabling them to use technology with ease and fluency. Moreover, Stillman (2020) stated that the digital world was evolving with each new generation. Both Millennials and Generation Z had shown a strong interest in social media, using these platforms in similar ways.

However, each generation had distinct values and utilized these platforms for different purposes.

However, according to the Gen Z and Millennial's Survey conducted by Deloitte (2022), individuals from both the millennial and Generation Z cohorts grappled with elevated levels of stress and anxiety, especially among younger respondents. An extensive Deloitte survey encompassed over 23,000 individuals across 46 nations revealed that more than half of Gen Z individuals and slightly fewer than 40% of millennials indicated feeling stressed or anxious most of the time. The survey further highlighted a concerning pattern among Gen Z respondents, with less than half identifying their own mental health as their primary stressor.

Problem Number 8. Based on the findings, what program may be proposed?

The primary objective of this research was to determine the impact of a sense of belonging and online aggression on psychological well-being. It also examined the levels of sense of belonging, online aggression, and psychological well-being among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials. Thus, this will educate and provide awareness about the aforementioned variables.

With the findings of the study, the program was created to actively promote methods and approaches for controlling aggressive behavior when interacting online. The "EmpowerMind: Nurturing Connections, Resilience Online, and Mental Wellness" program for Filipino Generation Z and Millennials will be using methods and approaches designed to emphasize the importance of using digital platforms for advocacy and awareness-building, to learn techniques to manage their emotions, cope with challenges, and cultivate a greater sense of inner peace and well-being, and to promote a culture of inclusivity and mutual respect within the community.

The program fosters a supportive digital environment that enhances users' sense of belonging. It helps individuals feel recognized, included, and connected to a community of like-minded people, thereby enhancing their overall well-being through positive online interactions. Additionally, it encourages empathy, respect, and inclusion within digital networks, resulting in more enjoyable user interactions. The program aims to improve communication skills, conflict resolution techniques, and appreciation of diverse perspectives, fostering an online culture of mutual respect and support. It also promotes mental wellness by providing participants with resources and support to address mental health issues related to online aggression. Participants learn coping strategies, self-care practices, and methods to maintain good mental health, leading to improved emotional well-being and resilience.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher has drawn the following conclusions:

That individuals often view their unique qualities as irrelevant in social groups, leading to feelings of loneliness and inadequacy. Familial belonging is crucial for personal development and well-being, and aligning with one's identity and beliefs can foster a strong sense of belonging.

That Filipino culture may exhibit subtle online aggression due to cultural norms promoting respect, harmony, and collective identity.

That these generations prioritize personal fulfillment, self-improvement, learning, and financial stability, influenced by societal, economic, and cultural factors that may result in somewhat low levels of psychological well-being.

That online aggression can be influenced by factors such as anonymity, social norms, reinforcement, and psychological traits, but its impact may not always be significant.

That online aggression negatively affects perpetrators' psychological well-being, leading to emotional and social strain. Factors like social exclusion, ethical dilemmas, and normalization of aggression also impact self-esteem and social support networks.

That belonging to a community does not guarantee meaningful relationships, as shallow or inadequate connections can lead to feelings of loneliness or alienation. Mental health is influenced by biological, psychological, socioeconomic, and cultural factors.

That Generation Z and Millennials are similar and have no distinctions between them. Despite potential differences in experiences, attitudes, and behaviors, both generations share common challenges related to psychological well-being, online aggression, and a sense of belonging, due to their close age proximity and shared cultural influences.

That the proposed program can be useful in providing awareness and lessening online aggression among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials and to further improve and enhance their sense of belonging and psychological well-being.

Based on the outlined findings and finalized conclusions, the following recommendations are provided:

Filipino Generation Z and Millennials may honor their sense of belonging by recognizing and valuing the diversity within their community. Appreciate each individual's unique identity and life experiences, by fostering an environment of acceptance and understanding of each other's differences.

By implementing research-based strategies, enhancing digital literacy and wellness—encompassing media literacy, critical thinking, and responsible online conduct—is crucial for minimizing the risk of online aggression. By encouraging Filipino Generation Z and Millennials to critically evaluate the content they consume and share, and by fostering empathy and respect for others, they can become more aware of the potential dangers and consequences of online aggression, including cyberbullying, harassment, and defamation.

Engaging in self-care activities, including employing diverse coping strategies and focusing on mental health, can enhance psychological well-being and overall quality of life. Cultivating self-awareness by reflecting on personal thoughts, emotions, and behaviors may help aid in identifying problem areas and making proactive changes.

Exploration of other factors like psychological resilience, social support, cultural dynamics, digital literacy, societal norms, and economic influences may help understand the limited impact of a sense of belonging and online aggression. Long-term and cross-cultural studies are crucial for developing targeted interventions to enhance online well-being and foster belonging.

Generation Z and Millennials show similar levels of sense of belonging, online aggression, and psychological well-being. Investigating shared social experiences, digital behaviors, and cultural influences can provide insights.

Public health professionals and psychology practitioners may help enhance psychological well-being without placing excessive emphasis on a sense of belonging, by investigating various factors such as social support networks, environmental factors, genetics, neurobiology, lifestyle choices, spirituality, education, emotional intelligence, leisure activities, workplace culture, and conduct cross-cultural research. Comprehensive understanding of these diverse influences may help providing effective approaches to promote mental health.

For implementing the recommendations based on the proposed program, Community Leaders and Organizations, Educators, Healthcare providers and Psychology Practitioners might play a crucial role in fostering inclusive social environments to enhance the sense of belonging, educating about responsible online behavior to address aggression, and providing accessible mental health resources for well-being. Continuous evaluation ensures effectiveness and responsiveness to evolving needs, aiming to cultivate supportive communities that promote individual welfare and positive online interactions.

Future researchers may enhance their understanding of the sense of belonging, experiences with online aggression, and psychological well-being among Filipino Generation Z and Millennials by considering the unique cultural, societal, and historical factors that shape their experiences. They may explore how cultural identity, family dynamics, and societal norms influence these aspects, as well as investigate the intersection of factors such as gender, sexual orientation, socioeconomic status, and geographic location. Utilizing mixed methods approaches is recommended to capture the complex interactions involved. Additionally, adopting a multi-generational perspective may provide deeper insights into the intricate relationships between sense of belonging, online aggression, and psychological well-being within the Filipino community. Studies on how online aggression may impact psychological well-being and vice versa, emphasizing their reciprocal influence may be conducted. Longitudinal studies may reveal how these interactions evolve, while qualitative research may uncover underlying mechanisms and individual experiences. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for developing effective interventions to mitigate the negative effects of online aggression and promote healthier online environments.

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